

GENERAL ISSUES OF IMAGE PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS AND CAPABILITIES OF WEB PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, general issues of image processing and analysis and provides information about the capabilities of web programming languages. Images can be obtained not only in the visible frequency range of electromagnetic waves, but also in the frequency range of acoustic, infrared, ultraviolet, ultrasound, X-ray waves and gamma rays. The means of their creation and preservation are very diverse. Scientific research, production and new methods of creating and storing information in the form of images, as well as the increase in the speed of use and application of modern tools, increase the volume of such information.

Keywords: image processing, hypertext, graphics, measurement, visualization. Html,

A person receives information about the environment mainly through his eyes. Therefore, any information given in the form of an image will be more understandable for us. Therefore, in many cases, information is interpreted in the form of graphs, maps, drawings, black-and-white and color images, notes, etc., in order to facilitate human learning. Information in the form of various images plays a very important role in human life, and it is impossible to replace it with something else that more fully interprets the essence of information.

It is known that images are not only the result of research in various fields of science, technology and economy, but also the object of processing, analysis and interpretation. Until recently, these tasks were performed directly by humans using their capabilities or mostly semi-automatically.

The big difference between the speed of image information acquisition and its processing and analysis has turned the issue of image processing and analysis automation into one of the most pressing issues of today. In the early 1960s, research on the development of devices and methods for automating image processing and analysis began in developed countries, optical-mechanical, optical-electronic, television, digital-analog computing devices and systems were discovered and used. In the process of processing images, computers with the necessary speed and memory, which contain devices for recording, outputting and displaying results (for example, on the screen), have a special place. The use of computers to process and analyze data on images has opened

up a vast new field of application. The use of computers for image processing and analysis, and the optional method of analysis and processing in a short time compared to the construction of models, made it possible to see the model - just perfect, even in cases that are not possible with modern technology, the accuracy and reliability of the results. and it allows for almost complete restoration, control of any step of the processing process, flexibility depending on the type and nature of the problem to be solved. That is why most automated systems for image processing and analysis are based on general purpose computers. It is clear that it is difficult to imagine solving any problem related to image processing and analysis without the use of computers.

Computer graphics deals with the issues of visualizing non-visual information (that is, creating an image). Visualization is performed based on the classification (model) of the object that needs to be depicted. Currently, there are many visualization methods and algorithms that differ in what and how to display.

Examples of visualizations (in order of increasing complexity) include:

- graph of functions;
- diagrams;
- geographical maps;
- animations.

It should be noted that graphs are static over time. Some of the games found in computer games change over time. In others, it creates an illusion that depicts changes occurring with real-world objects.

Image processing is a matter of image replacement. For image processing algorithms, the input is both images and the output is images. An example of this can be the image transmission system. In this system, the issues of low-volume encoding of data and reduction of noise in the image should be solved.

Image processing can be a matter of improving the quality of images depending on a certain criterion (for example, restoring the image, changing colors, increasing contrast), or making special substitutions that fundamentally change them.

The problem of image recognition is to obtain several images (characteristics) of an image entered into the system, or to determine whether this image belongs to any of the predefined classes. Visual object detection is somewhat the opposite of computer graphics. Because creating an image based on the given descriptions is a matter of computer graphics, creating its

descriptions is a matter of determining the descriptions. But this description can be different in each of these issues.

Image processing and analysis are used in all areas of human activity that involve images and where computers can be used. According to the opinion of many experts and scientists, the development of the theory of numerical processing and analysis of images and the development of computing tools led to the birth of a new field of science and technology with a bright future.

Over the next decade, the field of application of numerical image processing and analysis has expanded significantly. This was greatly influenced by the decrease in the size and price of computers, and the increase in the speed of operation, and the development of industrial copies of devices for inputting, outputting and displaying images on machines.

Image processing and analysis methods are already playing an important role in scientific investigations, information systems, medicine, biology, military work, geodesy, mapping, etc. Examples of the use of these methods include the digital transmission of information from spaceships, videotelephone communication through telephone lines, improving the clarity of images taken from an electron microscope, improving the quality of images taken from space, creating and improving the quality of earth surface features and natural images based on photographs taken from satellites (roentgenogram, thermogram). , radioisotope diagnostics, images, etc.), automated mapping based on planetary images, X-ray detection of defects in industrial equipment, etc. Therefore, digital processing and analysis of images has already become a profession for many people.

There is no doubt that in time digital processing and analysis of images will take an even wider place in various fields of science, technology and economy, in short, in almost all aspects of human activity.

A person encounters various images in his work. This challenge of automating image processing and preserving the source and results requires classifying the most common storage, image logging tools and methods into classes.

Data stored in electronic computers, which are the main working tools of image processing issues, impose certain requirements on their access and processing algorithms, sequence of processing steps, etc. Looking at the problem of numerical processing and analysis of images from this point of view, image processing can be divided into the most important stages, depending on the completeness of content on the one hand, data storage and management, the

appearance of machine algorithms, and the nature of the calculation process organization on the other:

1. Image conversion involves entering images into computer memory, representing image data using numerical values to efficiently store images at different levels of memory. The solutions used here should be evaluated primarily from the point of view of data storage in electronic computing machines and subsequent necessary processing. The main processes at this stage are discretization, quantization, and storing images in computer memory.

2. The main goal of the image preprocessing stage is to preserve the structure and form of the source image tariff. The performed substitutions produce images that belong to the source image class. For example, a source image in the form of a numerical matrix is transferred to a new, but still unique, image in the form of a numerical matrix as a result of preliminary processing, that is, sharpened. This action is carried out at the expense of strengthening the fragments. The main actions of this stage are to improve image quality and restore lost information.

3. At the stage of rendering the images into a two-color view, operations of creating or separating linear structures from the images are performed. At this stage, it is much easier to make images into a linear or graphical view, to analyze it, to measure its parameters. The main operations of this stage are image segmentation, outline, and skeleton separation.

4. At the stage of image analysis, the image and the objects in it are classified by measuring various parameters in fragments, etc., and identifying their signs. The main operations of this stage are the process of measuring spectral, topological, geometric, statistical structure and other features.

5. In image classification and recognition, it is usually the main decisive step in numerical processing and analysis of images. Using the results of the analysis, the image and its objects are divided into classes and selected. It is not necessary to apply these steps in their entirety to any practical problem, and at the same time, they are not required to be performed in the given order. For example, the classification of images into classes and the problem of identification can be performed directly on the source image obtained in the first step, without any other steps.

Capabilities of web programming languages in image processing

Since the WWW service of the Internet depends mainly on web pages, how are they created? it is natural to ask. HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) is a language based on SGML (Standard Generalized Markup Language) and

conforms to the international ISO 8879 standard. Web pages are written in HTML.

The simplicity of the HTML language (compared to SGML) and the availability of high formatting options made it popular among users. In addition, it was possible to use hypertexts. As the language developed, additional multimedia (image, sound, animation, etc.) capabilities were added to it. HTML is not considered a programming language. A simple Windows text editor such as Notepad is enough to prepare a document (web page) in this language. HTML commands are written between "<" and ">" symbols and are called descriptors or tags. For example, the entry marks the beginning of an HTML document.

So, HTML is a language written using descriptors in a simple text editor. An HTML document is an HTML text file with descriptors that make up a web page. An HTML document file name extension is ".html" and may also be saved as ".htm" in some cases. When an HTML document is loaded into memory using web browsers, it appears on the screen as a web page.

The HTML language is (regularly) evolving. In turn, web browsers are being updated. Currently, HTML.4 language is mainly used to prepare a web page. Some of its commands cannot be executed by old web browsers (Internet Explorer-3, Internet Explorer-4). In addition, different web browsers, such as Internet Explorer and Netscape, are also slightly different from each other. Therefore, the same HTML document may appear slightly differently in different web browsers.

HTML mainly uses tags. `<html></html>` — tags that remain the main tag are written inside this tag. `<body></body>` - this is the body part of our page `<p></p>` - as you can see for writing a paragraph each tag is opened with `< >` and closed with `</>`. You can also use Notepad to learn HTML. Or you can use NotePad++ and similar editors.

In the beginning, the WWW system was designed to represent textual information, and HTML was developed as a text formatting language. Currently, HTML is the most popular language on the WWW. An HTML document is a text file that stores information and formatting instructions.

Tags are tools that establish communication between documents and format information.

Web page text and tags are placed in a single file called an HTML document.

The way your web page looks in a browser depends on the tags you choose and apply. There are hundreds of tags for formatting and placing

information in HTML. For example: `<p>` and `</p>` tags form a paragraph, and a pair of `<i>` and `</i>` tags indicates that the text between them should be italicized. Tags are also used to create a hypertext reference. With the help of hypertext references, the user can call up another document by left-clicking on a piece of text or an image. The HTML language is constantly being improved. Obsolete elements are removed, and new ones are added to the language. However, the HTML structure remains the same.

HTML commands are given using special elements called tags, that is, tags are the basis of it. The tags are enclosed in "`< >`" brackets, they are not visible in the browser and serve to make them look convenient. Usually, most tags are repeated twice and given in pairs, that is, "open and close". For example, `<BODY>`, `</BODY>`.

In the body of HTML, tags are capitalized and start with `< HTML >` and end with `</ HTML >`. It is not case sensitive.

It is also recommended to include `<HEAD>` and `<BODY>` tags in the document according to the HTML language template. When a browser reads an HTML document, their presence clearly indicates document sections. Even if they are not, the browser will read the HTML document correctly, the sections of the document will not be separated from each other.

Thus, a properly structured HTML document has the following structure:

`< HTML >`

`<HEAD>`

Information about the header `< / HEAD>`

`<BODY>`

Body of the document `< / BODY>`

`</ HTML >`

In this case, the header information section between `< HEAD>` and `< / HEAD>` is usually ignored by the user, but information is given to the browser. Between `< BODY>` and `< / BODY>`, its complete sequence of operators is placed. For example: `< HTML >`

`<HEAD>`

`< TITLE> My 1 web < /TITLE>` (for the header of this window) `< / HEAD>`

`<BODY>`

`<p>My first web page </p>` (for this edit window) `< / BODY>`

`</ HTML >`

Javascript language Webin connection with the "client-server" architecture when creating pages`a problem arises. Pages can be created both on

the client side and on the server side. In 1995, specialists of the Netscape company developed the JavaScript programming language and created a mechanism for managing pages on the client side.

Thus, Javascript is a language for handling client-side hypertext web browsing scenarios. To be more specific, Javascript is not just a client-side programming language. Liveware is a descendant of Javascript and is a Netscape server-side engine. But what makes Javascript popular is client-side programming.

JavaScript Its main function is to enable the user to change the values of the attributes of HTML containers and the properties of the rendering environment during viewing of HTML headers, in other words, to make them dynamic headers (DHTML). It can also be noted that headers are not reloaded, in practice this can be done by, for example, changing the background color of the header or the image in the document, opening a new window, or displaying a warning window. The name "JavaScript" is a proprietary product of Netscape. The language implemented by Microsoft is officially called Jscript. Jscript versions are compatible with corresponding versions of Javascript (not to be exact).

JavaScript- standardized by ECMA (European Computer Manufacturers Association). The corresponding standards are ECMA-262 and ISO-16262. These standards define the ECMAScript language, roughly equivalent to Javascript 1.1. Note that not all versions of Javascript today are ECMA compliant. In all of this information or manuals, we use the name Javascript.

Basic features of Javascript. Javascript is a relatively simple object-oriented language for building small client and server applications for the Internet. Programs written in Javascript are placed inside an HTML document and transferred along with them. Operating programs (browsers - browser from the English word) Netscape Navigator and Microsoft Internet Explorer transmit and execute programs (Scriptcode) placed in the text of the document.

Thus, Javascript is considered an interpreted programming language.

JavaScript Examples of programs created in

Examples of programs created in JavaScript include programs that check user input, perform certain actions when opening or closing a document. Such programs respond to instructions given by the user - clicking a mouse button, entering data on the screen, or moving the mouse around the page. It does work. In addition, programs in JavaScript are used in the browser and can also manage the attributes of the document.

You don't need any additional tools to create programs in JavaScript - only the appropriate version of JavaScript can be used. You will need a browser and a text editor that allows you to create DHTML documents. Since the JavaScript program is placed directly in HTML documents, the result of the program can be viewed using the document browser. It can be checked through a browser and if necessary, it is subject to change.

Features of the JavaScript programming language. With its help, you can dynamically control the appearance and structure of HTML documents.

Any HTML codes can be inserted into the document displayed on the screen during the process of syntactic analysis of the document loaded by the browser. With the help of the "Document" object, new documents can be created automatically depending on the previous actions of the user or other factors.

You can control the behavior of the browser using JavaScript. For example, the Window object has methods that allow you to display floating windows, create new browser windows, open and close them, set window running and size modes, and so on.

JavaScript allows interaction with the user. The most important feature of this language is the ability to define event processing - an optional part of the program code that is executed when a certain event (usually an action performed by the user) occurs. JavaScript provides the ability to perform arbitrary mathematical calculations. In addition, this language has advanced tools for working with time and date values. JavaScript was created as an alternative language to CGI programs and the Perl programming language, and as a complement in some cases to Java.

The main question of every beginning programmer is: "How are programs created and executed?". We'll try to answer this question as simply as possible, but not forgetting all the ways JavaScript code can be used.

First, JavaScript code is executed by the browser. It has a dedicated JavaScript interpreter. The execution of the program depends on when and how the interpreter takes control.

This, in turn, depends on the functional application of the code.

In general, it is possible to distinguish 4 different ways of functional use of JavaScript:

1. *hypertext link (URL scheme);*
2. *event processing (handler);*
3. *replace (entity);*
4. *put (SCRIPT container).*

PHP programming language. PHP was created as a result of the development of another software product, PHP/FI. PHP/FI was created in 1995 by Rasmus Lerdorf as a simple set of Perl scripts to track referrals to his online resume. He called this set of scripts Personal Contents Page Tools. Because more functionality was required, Rasmus created an extended implementation of C that was able to work with a database, allowing users to create simple dynamic Web applications. Rasmus released the PHP/FI code to the public so that anyone can extend and modify it.

PHP/FI, Personal Contents Page / Forms Interpreter, had the core functionality of current PHP. It had Perl-like variables, automatic interpretation of form variables, and HTML-like syntax. The syntax itself was reminiscent of Perl, only more limited, simplified, and incomplete. In 1997, PHP/FI 2.0, the second version of the C implementation, had several thousand fans worldwide and was installed on approximately 50,000 domains. This was 1% of all Internet domains. Since many people contributed their code blocks to this project, it is no longer a one-person project.

PHP/FI 2.0 was officially released only in November 1997. Until then, it was mainly available in the form of beta releases. Soon after, the first alpha PHP 3.0 was released. PHP 3.0 was the first version of what PHP looks like today. It was created by Andi Gutmans and Zeev Suraski in 1997 as a complete rewrite of the language because they found PHP/FI 2.0 to be insufficient for building their own eCommerce applications. To join forces, Andi, Rasmus, and Zeev created and released PHP 3.0 as the official successor to PHP/FI 2.0. As a result, development of PHP/FI 2.0 has stopped. One of the greatest strengths of PHP 3.0 was its extensibility. It has encouraged dozens of users to create new extension modules because it provides limited users with a robust infrastructure and extensibility for various databases, protocols, and APIs. Perhaps this is the reason why PHP 3.0 is so popular. One of the main features of PHP 3.0 was object-oriented syntax.

The language was named PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor. By late 1998, PHP was the foundation for tens of thousands of users and hundreds of thousands of Web sites. At its peak, PHP 3.0 was installed on approximately 10% of the Internet's Web servers. PHP 3.0 was officially released in June 1998 after 9 months of public testing.

PHP4. After the official release of PHP 3.0 in the winter of 1998, Andi Gutmans and Zeev Suraski began reworking the PHP core in order to improve the performance of working with large applications and increase the modularity

of the PHP code base. Creating such applications was possible in PHP 3.0, but PHP 3.0 was not designed to serve complex applications.

In addition to greatly increased performance, this version of PHP 4.0 introduced the following features: a large number of Web servers, the use of HTTP sessions, buffering of output, methods of safe handling of user input, and various new language constructs.

PHP 4 is currently the last version of PHP. Work has begun on improvements and modifications to integrate Zend Engine with PHP 5.0.

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